

Early-Stage Detection of Psoriasis using Deep Learning Approach of Convolutional Neural Network and Generative Adversarial Network

Pushendra Kumar Dwivedi
Quantum University, Roorkee,
Uttarakhand, India

Dr. Vivek Kumar
Professor, Quantum
University, Roorkee,
Uttarakhand, India

Dr. Manoj Kumar Panda
Professor, WIT, Dehradun,
Uttarakhand, India

Abstract— In skin disease detection CASD (Computer aided skin diagnosis) plays major role. Non-invasive screening of Psoriasis plays a crucial role in dermatology. In this study Psoriasis dataset to predicts skin diseases by using multiple GAN (Generative Adversarial Network) models and Ensemble model. In GAN, traditional GAN and DEBLUR GAN are used and then trained 5 ensemble CNN (convolutional neural network) models on different train and test data. Comparative performance between traditional, DEBLUR and Ensemble Model is calculated using different performance metrics. Ensemble GAN CNN model outperforms than traditional augmentation CNN model and deblur GAN augmentation CNN model. Performance accuracy of 99.8737% is observed for proposed model.

Keywords :Psoriasisdetection, convolutional neural network, Generative Adversarial Network, Ensemble model

I. INTRODUCTION

Your doctor will ask about your health and check at your skin, hair, nails. Then, y medical professional may take a sample of skin for microscopic analysis. This will helps to find out other conditions and identify the kind of psoriasis. A skin specialist will check your skin and scalp for probability of psoriasis before making a plan of diagnosis.

With mortality rate of 1 death every 6 individuals; One of the major reason of death in the modern period is cancer. In 2019, there were 18 million new instances of cancer and 9.5 million cancer-caused deaths, according to the American Cancer Society [1].One of the most critical malignancies in USA is skin cancer. Melanoma is the deadlier of the two main types of skin cancer, with a five-year survival rate estimated at roughly 98% if diagnosed early and 22% if detected later [2].

Melanoma was anticipated to have 96,470 new cases and up to 7,236 fatalities in 2019[3]. When a melanocyte, which makes the pigment melanin, starts to replicate uncontrolled, it might cause melanoma, which causes malignant tumours to grow. These cancerous tumours are commonly identified by the abbreviation ABCDE [4] and exhibit traits such asymmetry, irregular boundaries, a wide range of colours, a size greater than 6 mm, and a developing lesion.

The most crucial characteristics for melanoma diagnosis are colour and form out of all the qualities mentioned. The distribution of pigment, asymmetry or symmetry, heterogeneity or homogeneity, the amount of keratin on surface of skin, irregular or regular vascular morphology, the presence and absence of ulceration, the edge of the lesion, and the color of the lesion are the characteristics that define the structure. Making an early melanoma diagnosis involves taking into account a number of factors. Melanoma can be treated if it is found in its early stages. Many methods have been used in medical image processing to increase performance for a precise and fast diagnosis.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In this research, a deep neural network (DNN)- technique for psoriasis detection was put forth. Convolutional and fully-connected learnt layers make up the majority of the suggested approach. The

input image is processed using these four convolutional layers to extract some useful multilayer characteristics. The feature maps are down-sampled using the max-pooling procedure to speed up the deep network. A classifier uses fully connected layers that resemble the classic multi-layer perceptron neural networks. The suggested technique may successfully determine whether the input image is psoriasis, according to experimental findings.[1]

Psoriasis is a skin condition that causes chronic inflammation and has no known cause. The extensor, lower back, and scalp, portions of the limbs all exhibit red and silvery scaly plaques as the disease's outward sign. Psoriasis is currently a major focus for the creation of new drugs after receiving little attention for a number of years. A network of tightly linked genes that have varied levels of co-expression may function as molecular markers for an underlying trait. New molecular targets for psoriasis have been found using a system biology method called weighted gene coexpression network analysis (WGCNA). Five gene modules were identified from the analysis of gene co-expression interactions in 58 samples of psoriatic lesions, and they were clustered according to the patterns of gene co expression. Three psoriatic datasets were used to validate the co expression pattern.

From each module, 10 highly interconnected and instructive genes were chosen and designated as psoriasis specific hub signatures. These hallmark genes could be possibilities for the identification of biomarkers that reveal fresh targets for therapeutic intervention. WGCNA, the network-based technique, has offered a different way to identify the important psoriasis controllers and drivers. Other diseased conditions can be studied using the current work's study principle.[2]

In patients with psoriasis, asymptomatic joint involvement is recognised. It is unclear; nevertheless, if these patients go on to develop psoriatic arthritis (PsA). The current study's objectives were to investigate the prevalence of asymptomatic joint lesions, specifically enthesitis, in people with psoriasis vulgaris (PsV), and to further evaluate the clinical characteristics. 28 PsA and 18 PsV patients had positron emission tomography/computed tomography (PET/CT) exams using ¹⁸F-fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG). There have been reports of intergluteal, scalp, and nail involvements.

Notably, 6 out of 18 PsV patients (33%) with asymptomatic enthesitis had subclinical PsA. In subclinical PsA patients, psoriasis of the scalp, intergluteal membrane, and nails occurred more frequently than in PsV patients (100%, 83%, and 64%). The PsV and subclinical PsA groups did not differ in terms of ESR, WBC counts, or CRP. Asymptomatic enthesitis may be discovered using PET/CT imaging. Our research indicates that the subset of people with subclinical PsA was far larger than anticipated. Higher prevalence of intergluteal, scalp, and nail psoriasis supported the risk of PsA as previously documented. [3]

A chronic inflammatory skin condition known as psoriasis is characterised by scaly, erythematous skin and affects a number of systemic organs and tissues. Psoriatic arthritis (PsA), one of the various kinds of psoriasis, is frequently observed and can occasionally progress to a severe form of arthritis that causes joint dysfunction. There are many instruments, most notably questionnaires, to detect PsA in communities in Europe and America, but little is known about how useful these tools are in populations in Asia.

In this study, we looked into the effectiveness of the Psoriasis Epidemiology Screening Instrument (PEST) questionnaire as a representative tool for detecting PsA in psoriasis patients from Japan. In this study, 143 psoriasis sufferers in total were included. 29 of them had PsA, according to the diagnosis. Patients with PEST scores > 3 had significantly higher rates of PsA, with a specificity of 78.9% and a sensitivity of 93.1%. [4] Psoriatic cells develop more quickly than normal, healthy cells do in psoriasis skin condition. Due to the build-up of dead skin cells brought on by this rapid growth, the skin becomes thickly covered in red, dry, and itchy areas. Lesion diagnosis is made more difficult by the fact that these patches of psoriatic skin lesions may have traits that are comparable to those of healthy skin. Lesion segmentation, however, is crucial for the precise diagnosis of diseases and the determination of their severity. In that situation, our

team had already segmented psoriasis lesions using the traditional clustering approach. However, it is hampered by the restriction of fitting inside the clusters' regional sub-optimal centroids. [5]

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Here are three important steps in proposed method. First step of project is generating ensemble GAN Augmentation CNN model. Second stage is training the generated model with psoriasis dataset by training algorithm with multiple times to make efficient results due to unstable behaviour of CNN. There are many traditional techniques used in literature with even ensemble method but ensemble CNN provides less time consumption and less computational complexity. In this application 5 CNNs are ensemble to get improved performance for Psoriasis detection. From each network classification, average probability is calculated to get final classification results.

Figure 1: Proposed Method Flowchart

Proposed method has basic 4 steps

1. Psoriasis dataset selection
2. Pre-processing
3. Ensemble CNN method
4. Test data analysis and performance Analysis

Dataset selection is one of the most important steps in proposed method.

Figure 2: Block Diagram of proposed ensemble classifier

Above graph shows there are total 5 CNNs are ensembled with average probability to get final classification results.

A.RESULT ANALYSIS

Proposed method and existing technique results are compared to show the proposed model performance is superior than existing **techniques**. All the metrics used for performance analysis are explained below

TABLE 1:CONFUSION MATRIX FOR EVALUATING CLASSIFICATION

Predicted ↓	Actual value	
	Normal	Disease Type
Normal Image	True Negative	False Negative
Skin Disease	False Positive	True Positive

The following table shows the confusion matrix, which has four true positive values. False positive, false negative and true negative

We look into the machine learning model's accuracy. We employ a confusion matrix since accuracy and appropriate classification are both required. An NxN matrix called a confusion matrix is used to assess how well the machine learning model handles the categorization problem. There are four variations of the confusion matrix TP, NT, FN, and FP.

We talk about the accuracy of the machine learning method for categorization using the confusion matrix.

B.ACCURACY

Accuracy is calculated as follows using confusion matrix,

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+FN+TN}$$

C. PRECISION

Precision here is the ratio of count of TP classes to the total of FP plus TP classes

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

C. RECALL

Recall is the ratio of the count of TP classes with the total of FN plus TP classes

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

D. F-SCORE

$$F\text{-score} = 2 \times \frac{Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall}$$

Here we will use a test using this module, and a machine algorithm will determine whether the test data is normal or have signs of Alzheimer's disease. We use the best categorization algorithm available. The user is presented with the final classification result and the likelihood that it is accurate after it has been created using user input in the form of a patient health record.

In the selected dataset two different folders are present called 'benign' and 'malignant'. In original dataset total 660 images are available.

Fig. 3 Traditional Augmented Image

Fig.4 Traditional Augmentation CNN model performance

Traditional GAN gives 85% accuracy and the confusion matrix graph of x-axis shows Predicted label and y-axis represents TRUE labels and blue color boxes contains INCORRECT PREDICTION count and different colour boxes contains correct prediction number.

Fig.5 CNN with DEBLUR GAN model performance

CNN with Deblur GAN gives superior performance compared to traditional augmentation CNN model.

Ensemble GAN Augmentation CNN Model Accuracy : 99.873737373737
 Ensemble GAN Augmentation CNN Model Precision : 99.88262910798123
 Ensemble GAN Augmentation CNN Model Recall : 99.86376021798364
 Ensemble GAN Augmentation CNN Model FMeasure : 99.8730327694086

Fig.6 Ensemble GAN Augmentation CNN model performance

With ensemble GAN Augmentation CNN model got 99.87% accuracy. Training 5 CNN ensemble models then voting and selecting model with best accuracy.

Fig.7 Bar Graphs for performance analysis

The x-axis in the graph above shows the names of the algorithms, while the coloured bars reflect various criteria like accuracy and precision. Y-axis represents accuracy values. we can see all algorithms values in tabular format and in all algorithms Ensemble CNN got high accuracy.

Fig.7 Traditional GAN Train and Test accuracy and lossy graph

In the graph of fig 7 x-axis represents training epoch and y-axis represents accuracy and lost values and yellow line represents test loss and red line indicates training lost and green line indicated training accuracy and blue line represents test accuracy and we can see in above graph that test loss is little high but overall, here we see that accuracy increased with each increasing epoch and loss is decreased.

Fig. 8 Deblur GAN Train and Test , accuracy and Loss Graph

In above deblur graph also we can see yellow colour line for test loss is still high. Deblur GAN augmentation CNN model provides superior performance compared to traditional augmentation CNN model.

Fig. 9 Ensemble GAN Train and Test, accuracy and Loss Graph

In above ensemble graph we can see test loss is dropped closer to 0 so ensemble model is good in performance compared to other Classifiers such as traditional augmentation CNN classifier and Deblur GAN augmented CNN model.

IV. CONCLUSION

Psoriasis detection using deep learning and GAN plays major role in dermatology as it helps to detect Psoriasis in non-invasive manner by computer aided diagnosis. In this study two existing technologies such as traditional CNN augmented, GAN deblur augmentation are compared with proposed Ensemble GAN CNN augmentation model. Proposed model outperforms the existing techniques. Different performance metrics like accuracy and precision, recall and F-score are calculated for giving superior performance of proposed model.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

All the work present by me here would be incomplete unless I express my gratitude towards those who supported and delightfully cooperated with me during this process.

I am very thankful to the Almighty and my family for bestowing their blessings at every moment and providing with ability, courage, resources, opportunity and their kind support.

I would like to thank Professor(Dr.) Vivek Kumar , Professor, Quantum University, Roorkee, Uttarakhand, India and Professor(Dr.) Manoj Kumar Panda, Professor, Women Institute of Technology, Dehradun, Uttarakhand for their intellectual and technical support throughout the my research work for PhD in Computer Science and Engineering.

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